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BACTERIAL CELLULOSE- POLYCAPROLACTONE COMPOSITES AS ENVIRONMENTAL MATERIALS

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Chemistry of poly(ϵ -caprolactone)

In our previous studies...

PCL-based Macromonomers

Mixture of 2-branched and 4-branched macromonomers

Modified with photo-reactive compound

Cross-linked membrane

Mixing of linear and 2- and 4- branched macromonomers for controlling melting point near body temperature

Table 1
Melting points and ΔH of cross-linked materials

Run	Molar ratio		Concentration (%)	T_m^a (°C)	ΔH^a (J/g)
	4b10-m	2b20-m			
1 ^b	100	0	50	–	–
2	90	10	50	–	–
3	80	20	50	–	–
4	70	30	50	30.7	20.2
5	60	40	50	32.7	34.2
6	50	50	50	33.9	35.5
7	40	60	50	35.5	39.3
8	30	70	50	37.4	44.4
9	20	80	50	38.9	46.0
10	10	90	50	41.0	54.0
11 ^c	0	100	50	42.7	56.7

^a The values were determined by DSC and indicated means by at least triplicated measurements.

^b T_m and ΔH values of 4b10-m before cross-linked were 42.5 °C and 88.1 J/g, respectively.

^c T_m and ΔH values of 2b20-m before cross-linked were 51.3 °C and 110 J/g, respectively.

Softening points were controlled by the mixing ratios of 2- and 4-branched PCL

ON-OFF drug permeation control near body temperature

ON-OFF permeation control could be achieved using cross-linked PCL membranes

Graft polymerization of CL on bacterial cellulose nanofibers

Fig. SEM view of bacterial cellulose

Fig. proposed micro-structure of PCL-grafted bacterial cellulose

Preparation of the suspension of PCL-grafted BC in CHCl_3

After scCO_2 dry substitution

run No.	BC		PCL		non-grafted PCL	
	[%]	[mg]	[%]	[mg]	$M_n(\times 10^3)$	M_w/M_n
1	58.92	125.21	41.08	87.29	9.3	1.66
2	37.50	73.09	62.50	121.81	25.3	1.70
3	16.72	51.96	83.28	258.84	84.9	1.65

Characterization of PCL-grafted BC

Fig. X-ray diffraction patterns (left fig.) and IR spectra (right fig.) of PCL-grafted BC

Thermal property of PCL-grafted BC

Fig. DSC curves (left fig.) of PCL-grafted BC non-grafted PCL (right fig.)

Preparations of PCL-grafted membranes by spray-coating

Thin film formation

Spray to the supporting membrane
(conventional filter paper)

Embedded PCL-grafted BC on the membrane

Thermo-responsive permeation control by PCL-grafted BC membrane

Fig. Thermo-responsive permeation control by PCL-grafted BC membrane